

Probabilistic literacy in compulsory education: Curriculum analysis in the Spanish context

Torres-Escoriza, Víctor^a and López-Martín, María del Mar^{a*} and Díaz-Levicoy, Danilo^b

^a*Departamento de Educación, Universidad de Almería, Almería, España;* ^b*Facultad de Ciencias Básicas, Universidad Católica del Maule, Talca, Chile.*

Abstract: In a data-driven society, probabilistic literacy is an essential skill for exercising critical and informed citizenship, which justifies analyzing its presence in the school curriculum. Within this framework, the research examines the treatment of probability in the current curriculum guidelines for compulsory education in Spain (6–16 years). A qualitative documentary approach is adopted, guided by Gal's (2005) model of probabilistic literacy. The results reveal a progressive and integrative approach, which evolves from intuitive interpretations in primary education to formalizations in compulsory secondary education. The early incorporation of subjective meaning and notions such as variability and uncertainty is observed, in contrast to the systematic absence of axiomatic meaning. Although components of functional and critical literacy are considered, the explication of critical thinking is concentrated in the final year of compulsory secondary education.

Keywords: Probabilistic literacy, curriculum, primary education, compulsory secondary education, meanings of probability

1. Introduction

In contemporary society, characterized by the constant production and circulation of data (Alsina et al., 2020), the informed interpretation of uncertain phenomena is a key skill for making informed decisions (Develaki, 2025). In this context, probability, as a discipline focused on modelling and communicating uncertainty, transcends the strictly mathematical realm and becomes relevant in contexts as diverse as medicine, economics, and engineering (Alsina & Vásquez, 2016a; Batanero, 2015; Ortiz et al., 2007).

In this context, probabilistic literacy, understood as the ability to understand, use and communicate probabilistic ideas in real and uncertain contexts (Gal, 2005), is an essential component of any citizen's education. This is not limited to mastering formal procedures, but also includes the development of critical thinking aimed at identifying random phenomena, assessing risks and making informed decisions (Borovcnik, 2016; Hokor, 2023; Nacarato & Grando, 2014). However, the consolidation of this competence faces

significant obstacles: the tendency to seek absolute certainties (Bórquez, 2025; Schulz et al., 2020), cognitive biases that condition reasoning (Gilovich et al., 2002), the persistence of teaching approaches focused on deterministic content (Batanero et al., 2004, Batanero, Burril, et al., 2011), and the lack of teacher training in this area (Franco & Alsina, 2022; Reyes-Astorga et al., 2025; Schoen et al., 2019).

From a curricular perspective, probability has historically received limited and uneven treatment in various countries (López & Gómez, 2022; Vásquez & Cabrera, 2022). In the US context, there are differing approaches: while the proposals of the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2003) advocate an introduction to qualitative notions associated with randomness from early childhood education onwards, the Common Core State Standards Initiative (CCSSI, 2010) place its teaching more systematically in secondary education. In countries such as Australia, Chile, New Zealand, Rwanda and Spain, probability is introduced in primary education through the recognition of the random nature of some experiences and an intuitive approach to calculating the probability of events, supported by the use of everyday language and situations familiar to students (Alsina & Vásquez, 2016a; Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority [ACARA], 2020; Chilean Ministry of Education [MINEDUC], 2012; Dushimimana et al., 2024; Gómez et al., 2015; Ministry of Education of New Zealand [MOE], 2015; Official State Gazette [BOE], 2014; Rwanda Education Board [REB], 2015).

The curriculum is conceived as an organized system of knowledge, practices and educational purposes that structures teaching throughout schooling, beyond a mere list of contents (Young, 2013). From this perspective, its quality depends fundamentally on the coherent organization and articulation of content over time, considering the epistemic structure of disciplines and the relationship between conceptual and procedural knowledge as the basis for deep learning (McPhail, 2021). Curricular coherence is thus defined as the logical and epistemological alignment of objectives, content, methods and assessment to promote meaningful learning (Borges et al., 2025), and is associated with better educational outcomes when it ensures progression and clarity between levels (Schmidt & Houang, 2012). This approach requires analysing the curriculum while also considering educational objectives, the role of teachers and the socio-educational context (Badmus et al., 2025).

This framework justifies the analysis of the treatment of probability in the Spanish curriculum, especially considering that, historically, this content has had a lesser presence compared to other mathematical blocks and, on occasions, has been subordinated to statistics (García-Alonso et al., 2025; López & Gómez, 2022). In this regard, the recent curriculum reform (BOE, 2022a; 2022b) offers an opportunity to examine the extent to which this trend has changed and the degree to which the institutional meanings currently promoted favour the development of probabilistic literacy.

To this end, this paper analyses the presence of probability in the curriculum regulations for compulsory education in Spain, identifying the meanings attributed to it, the advances

and limitations of its incorporation, and its implications for probabilistic literacy. Specifically, the following research questions are addressed:

- What elements of knowledge, dispositions and meanings of probability are promoted in the curricula of primary and compulsory secondary education in Spain?
- How are these elements articulated and progressed throughout compulsory education?
- What tensions, gaps or mismatches are identified in the curricular treatment of probability and what implications do they have for students' probabilistic literacy?

These questions guide the comparative and critical analysis of the Spanish curriculum, with the aim of generating evidence that contributes to improving the teaching of probability, initial and continuing teacher training, and the design of future educational reforms.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Components of probabilistic literacy

Gal's probabilistic literacy model (2005) conceives this construct as a multidimensional structure composed of five cognitive and three dispositional components, which act in an interrelated manner in the understanding, interpretation, and communication of uncertainty in everyday and social contexts. From this perspective, a person can be considered literate in probability not only when they know concepts and procedures, but also when they simultaneously integrate these components to interpret reality and make decisions.

Cognitive elements (see Table 1) refer to different types of knowledge necessary to understand and use probability, and include, among others, understanding fundamental ideas such as variability or randomness, the ability to estimate probabilities, the appropriate use of probabilistic language, the interpretation of probability in different contexts, and the formulation of critical questions in response to probabilistic messages. The integrated presentation of these cognitive components allows us to visualize how each one contributes to building a solid conceptual framework for reasoning with uncertainty. By analyzing these elements together, we can see that isolated mastery of definitions or procedures does not guarantee functional probabilistic literacy; on the contrary, it is the interaction between ideas, language, context, and critical thinking that enables a deep understanding and flexible use of probability in real-life situations.

Table 1. *Cognitive elements of probabilistic literacy (Gal, 2005)*

Elements of knowledge	Description
Big ideas in probability: Variability, randomness, independence, prediction, and uncertainty.	Variability implies recognizing that the results of a random event are not constant and may fluctuate due to different factors. Randomness refers to the property of a process or event in which the results are unpredictable and do not follow a deterministic pattern. Independence assumes that knowledge of one event does not provide information about the other and, therefore, the occurrence of one event does not affect the occurrence of the other. Predictability refers to the ability to anticipate the outcome of an event based on available information and observed patterns. Uncertainty is the lack of certainty about the outcome of an event. Uncertainty can arise from a lack of information, the complexity of a system, or the random nature of events.
Probability assignment: various ways of finding or estimating the probability of an event occurring.	Probability assignment in Gal's probabilistic literacy model refers to the process of assigning numerical values to the probability of certain events occurring. To calculate probabilities effectively, students must understand how to estimate, interpret, and communicate them. Although teaching focuses on classical and frequentist approaches, in practice estimates often combine elements of all three conceptions of probability: classical, frequentist, and subjective.
Language: the terms and methods used to communicate randomness.	Probabilistic language refers to the way probabilities and chance are represented and communicated. It is essential that students acquire a solid understanding of probabilistic language, which involves interpreting and communicating uncertainty through different representations, both numerical and verbal. This skill requires familiarity with concepts such as randomness and certainty, as well as the ability to move flexibly between different registers. Understanding that expressions such as 'there is an 80% probability' and 'it is very likely' communicate the same idea is key to the development of contextualized probabilistic thinking.
Context: Understanding the role and impact of probability in various events and processes.	Probability literacy involves not only mastery of concepts and procedures, but also the ability to interpret probability in real-world contexts. Understanding how uncertainty and randomness affect everyday events allows individuals to anticipate and evaluate variable situations. Thus, integrating practical examples into teaching enriches understanding, such as when a student recognizes that the probability of a bus running on time may change depending on specific circumstances, such as weather or extraordinary events.
Critical questions: Incorporation of questions that enable reflection and evaluation of the quality of the information.	The probability literacy model emphasizes the importance of asking critical questions to evaluate probabilistic statements, recognizing the influence of biases on reasoning. Five essential questions are proposed that address the context, source, process, meaning, and reflective interpretation of probabilistic information, facilitating rigorous and informed analysis.

Dispositional elements (see Table 2) refer to attitudes, beliefs, and affective orientations that mediate the way people interpret probabilistic information and cope with situations characterized by chance and uncertainty. These dispositions influence the inclination to examine uncertain situations, review intuitive judgements, and engage in critical and reflective questioning. Taken together, these components make it clear that probabilistic literacy involves an active disposition toward uncertainty, oriented toward analysis, self-regulation of judgement, and informed decision-making. From this perspective,

dispositional elements favour a conscious and contextualized use of probability in various areas of life.

Table 2. *Dispositional elements of probabilistic literacy (Gal, 2005)*

Dispositional elements	Description
Critical stance	Adopting a critical stance towards probabilistic data involves the ability to question, interpret and reflect on the validity, quality and context of the information presented. When faced with potentially biased, partial or manipulated messages, it is essential that students develop the ability to ask questions that enable them to evaluate sources, methods, representativeness, interpretation and possible biases.
Beliefs and attitudes	Affective dimensions (emotions, attitudes, and beliefs) play a key role in how individuals understand and apply probability. Promoting positive self-perception in relation to probabilistic reasoning allows individuals to face uncertainty with greater objectivity, avoiding interpretations influenced by anecdotal experiences or personal biases.
Personal feelings in the face of uncertainty and risk	The degree of uncertainty or predictability experienced can be the basis for one's own perception and ability to assess the risks associated with significant events or outcomes in life.

2.2. *Meanings of probability*

Probability has been interpreted in various ways throughout history, reflecting both the evolution of its mathematical formalization and different philosophical, cognitive and didactic perspectives. There is therefore no single agreed meaning, but rather a plurality of approaches that coexist and complement each other. In the field of education, recognizing this diversity is essential, as it allows us to understand which concepts are promoted in curricula, anticipate the difficulties that students may experience and take advantage of the educational potential of each interpretation (Batanero, 2005).

Intuitive meaning arises from spontaneous perceptions of certainty, possibility or risk, which are expressed in everyday language through terms such as *certain*, *possible*, *impossible*, *more likely* or *less likely* (Batanero, Díaz, et al., 2011; Vásquez & Alsina, 2017). From an operational point of view, this meaning is characterized by a qualitative assessment of events, without resorting to calculations or the assignment of numerical values. This initial level is fundamental as it allows for an initial understanding of uncertainty and lays the foundations for the development of subsequent probabilistic learning (Serrano-Díaz, 2022). In situations where this meaning emerges, a certain degree of objectivity may be present, insofar as different people may arrive at the same judgement based on direct observation of the context, without the intervention of prior experience, additional information or belief updating processes.

The *classical or Laplacian meaning* represents the first mathematical formalization of this concept. Formulated by Laplace (1814), it defines the probability of an event as the ratio between the number of favourable cases and the total number of possible cases, under the condition that all of them are equally probable (Batanero, 2005). This approach introduces a normative view of probability and allows well-structured situations to be

addressed using systematic calculation procedures. However, the applicability of this meaning is limited, as the hypothesis of equiprobability is not always realistic and cannot be extended to more complex or contextualized situations (Batanero et al., 2016).

The *frequency meaning* introduces an empirical and experimental perspective, conceiving the probability of an event as the value towards which its relative frequency tends when an experiment is repeated a large number of times under stable conditions (Batanero, 2005; Alsina & Vásquez, 2016b; Gómez et al., 2015). From this approach, probability is not determined in advance or exactly, but is estimated from the observed results, which underlines its approximate nature and dependence on the number of trials performed. This behaviour is based on the law of large numbers, which explains why the indefinite repetition of an experiment leads to the emergence of empirical regularities (Batanero, 2005). In situations where equiprobability can be assumed, these regularities allow a conceptual relationship with the classical meaning to be established.

The *subjective meaning* conceives probability as a degree of personal belief about the occurrence of an event, conditioned by the available information, prior knowledge, and context of the individual making the judgement (Batanero & Díaz, 2007). From this perspective, probability is interpreted as a rational assessment by the subject when making decisions in contexts of uncertainty (Elliott, 2024). Subjective probability can be expressed both qualitatively and quantitatively, insofar as it represents different degrees of belief, and allows different people to assign different probabilities to the same event based on the information available to them. A central feature of this meaning is the conditional and revisable nature of probabilities, since the incorporation of new information may lead to a modification of the probability initially assigned. This revision is explained by the Bayesian approach, which distinguishes between a priori probability (before incorporating new information) and a posteriori probability (after considering it), and which uses Bayes' theorem as a rule for consistently updating beliefs based on available evidence.

Axiomatic meaning constitutes the culmination of the mathematical formalization of probability. Formulated by Kolmogorov (1933), it conceives probability as a function that assigns each event in a sample space a number between 0 and 1, and which satisfies three essential axioms: non-negativity ($P(A) \geq 0$), additivity for disjoint events ($P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B)$), and normalization ($P(\Omega) = 1$, where Ω is the sample space) (Batanero, 2005; Godino et al., 1996). Based on set theory and measure theory, this approach consolidated the modern framework of probability by providing a unified theoretical model independent of empirical or philosophical interpretations. Its main strength lies in conceiving probability as an abstract entity, capable of integrating the various previous meanings into a general mathematical structure, as well as maintaining a close connection with other branches such as algebra, analysis, and measure theory (Batanero et al., 2016; Serrano-Díaz, 2022).

In summary, the different meanings of probability, from the intuitive to the axiomatic, illustrate the cognitive progression and complexity of knowledge in this field. Its proper integration into the curriculum is key to consolidating probabilistic literacy in compulsory

education and, in the case of Spain, to assessing the real scope of recent educational reforms.

3. Methodology

The research is based on a qualitative documentary approach (Bisquerra, 2019), focusing on the analysis of the regulatory texts governing compulsory education in Spain. Content analysis was adopted as the study method (Krippendorff, 2019), as it was considered suitable for systematically examining the explicit and implicit information contained in official curricula. The study is descriptive in nature (Neuendorf, 2016), as it does not seek to evaluate implementation in school practice, but rather to characterize the presence and treatment of probability in the documents analyzed.

The research phases followed were: (1) selection of the current official curricula for primary and compulsory secondary education in Spain, (2) detailed reading of the texts to identify sections related to probability, (3) deductive categorization based on the conceptual framework presented, which integrates the components of probabilistic literacy by Gal (2005) and the different meanings of probability (Batanero, 2005), (4) coding and systematic classification of relevant fragments.

The analysis was initially carried out by one of the researchers, after which the preliminary results were reviewed, discussed and agreed upon by the research team, which specializes in the field of statistical education. This procedure reinforced the consistency of the analysis and ensured both the reliability and validity of the results.

3.1. Sample

The study sample consists of the official curricula for Primary Education (BOE, 2022a) and Compulsory Secondary Education (CSE) (BOE, 2022b) in Spain, regulated by Royal Decree 157/2022 and Royal Decree 217/2022, respectively, in accordance with Organic Law 3/2020 (LOMLOE). These regulations place the competency-based approach at the heart of the curriculum, guiding teaching towards the comprehensive education of students. Within this framework, the documents analyzed establish the minimum requirements for teaching at the national level, organized around the key competences that underpin the curriculum reform.

In the case of primary education, the curriculum is structured in three cycles of two years, covering a total of six years of compulsory schooling (BOE, 2022a). At this stage, mathematics is organized into mathematical concepts, which group knowledge around major conceptual and functional themes, such as numerical sense, algebraic sense, geometric sense, sense of measurement and stochastic sense, the latter of which integrates probability and statistics (BOE, 2022a).

For its part, CSE comprises four years, organized sequentially, and culminates in the fourth year with a diversification of the mathematics curriculum, which is offered in two modalities (Applied Mathematics and Academic Mathematics) depending on the academic orientation of the students (BOE, 2022b). As in primary education, the

regulations organize the curriculum around specific skills, basic knowledge and assessment criteria, maintaining the logic of mathematical meaning, albeit with a greater degree of explicitness and formalization in line with the stage.

3.2. Categories of analysis

The analysis of basic knowledge related to probability was carried out using a deductive categorization procedure (Krippendorff, 2019). The categorization was based on the elements of the conceptual framework described in Section 2, structured around two complementary analytical axes: on the one hand, the cognitive components (big ideas, procedures, language, contexts and critical questions) and dispositional components (critical stance, beliefs and attitudes, and personal feelings) of probabilistic literacy (Gal, 2005) and, on the other, the meanings of probability (intuitive, subjective, frequentist, classical, and axiomatic) (Batanero, 2005).

A two-dimensional qualitative coding system (x,y) was applied, where the first component (x) is associated with the degree of presence of the variables in the curriculum, distinguishing three categories:

- Absent (A), when the element of knowledge, dispositional or meaning considered is not present in the specific cycle or course of the curriculum regulations.
- Implicit (I), when the element of knowledge, disposition or meaning is not explicitly stated in the curriculum but is necessary to achieve the objectives or carry out the tasks planned for the stage.
- Explicit (E), when the element of knowledge, disposition or meaning constitutes a focus of instruction and direct assessment, appearing mentioned in the text.

The second component (y) refers to the relevance given to each variable, differentiating between:

- High (AL), when the knowledge, dispositional or meaning element is fundamental to achieving a direct (explicit) competency objective or a central (implicit) objective.
- Moderate (M), when the knowledge, dispositional or meaning element is developed in a cross-cutting or superficial manner.
- Low (L), when the knowledge, dispositional or meaning element has minimal or no contribution.

On this basis, an analysis matrix was developed to guide the identification and coding of relevant textual fragments from the official curricula.

4. Results

This section presents the main findings of the analysis of the curriculum regulations for primary and compulsory secondary education in relation to the teaching of probability. The results are organized according to the categories of analysis defined in the methodology section, which allows us to identify both the elements of knowledge and disposition and the progression of the different meanings of probability in the official curricula.

Before presenting the results, it is worth clarifying some aspects relating to the organization of the curriculum analysis. Firstly, the 1st and 2nd years of primary education are not included, as probability is not included in the curriculum for this cycle. In the case of compulsory secondary education, the 1st, 2nd and 3rd years have been analyzed together, as they are treated equally in terms of basic knowledge, specific competences and assessment criteria related to probability. The 4th year of CSE is examined independently, although without distinguishing between the two Mathematics options (Academic and Applied), since both incorporate the same curricular treatment of probability content.

4.1. Results in relation to Knowledge Elements

The information collected in Table 3 allows for a comparative analysis of the distribution and progression of the cognitive elements of probabilistic literacy throughout compulsory education. The comparative analysis between courses reveals a differentiated and non-homogeneous curricular progression in the cognitive elements of probabilistic literacy, in which components with an early and stable presence coexist alongside others that are clearly delayed. Concepts such as predictability, uncertainty and estimation are given explicit and highly relevant treatment from primary education onwards, which is maintained throughout compulsory schooling. In this context, both predictability and uncertainty are conceived as subjective measures applicable to everyday life, as reflected in the curriculum regulations when referring to probability as a ‘subjective measure of uncertainty’ and to the ‘recognition of uncertainty in everyday situations’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498). This pattern suggests that, from the earliest stages, the curriculum prioritises an approach to probability geared towards interpreting uncertain situations and making informed decisions, rather than the progressive mastery of complex formal structures. In contrast, independence constitutes a unique case of curricular delay, as it remains absent until the 4th year of CSE, where it is introduced directly as an explicit and central element linked to ‘the planning and analysis of composite experiments’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744), without any intermediate progression that would favour its gradual construction. This abrupt leap highlights a discontinuity in the treatment of a structural idea of probabilistic literacy.

With regard to probability assignment, the longitudinal comparison shows a progressive coexistence of approaches. While estimation is consolidated early on as a central element through ‘quantification and subjective estimation’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24502), probabilistic

calculation is introduced in the final cycle of primary education and consolidated in secondary education, focusing on obtaining numerical values ‘by applying Laplace's rule and counting techniques’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744). This overlap suggests that the curriculum does not replace the initial approaches with more formal ones, but rather progressively incorporates new procedures.

Table 3. *Gal's (2005) elements of knowledge in the curriculum regulations*

Category	Variable	3rd and 4th grade	5th and 6th grade	1st, 2nd, and 3rd year of secondary education	4th year of secondary education
Big ideas	Variability	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, M)	(E, H)
	Randomness	(I, M)	(I, M)	(E, H)	(I, M)
	Independence	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, L)	(E, H)
	Predictability	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Uncertainty	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
Probability assignment	Estimation	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Calculation	(A, M)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
Language	Verbal	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Numerical	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Graphical	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, M)	(E, H)
	Tabular	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, M)	(E, H)
Context	Personal	(I, H)	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, M)
	Work	(I, L)	(I, L)	(I, M)	(I, H)
	Scientific	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Social	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, H)
Critical questions	Context	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, L)	(E, H)
	Source	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, M)	(E, H)
	Process	(I, M)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Meaning	(E, H)	(I, H)	(I, M)	(I, M)
	Reflective interpretation	(I, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)

Note: (x, y), where x is presence and y is relevance; A: Absent, I: Implicit, E: Explicit, H: High, M: Moderate, and L: Low

Probabilistic language analysis reveals a clearly asymmetrical development, in which verbal and numerical registers acquire an explicit and highly relevant character from primary education onwards, while graphic and tabular registers remain absent during this stage and only become explicitly present in the 4th year of compulsory secondary education. Specifically, from the second cycle of primary education onwards, the regulations promote the use of verbal language to describe chance by means of the ‘identification of certain, possible and impossible events’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498), and, in a complementary manner, it introduces numerical language linked to estimation and calculation processes at an early stage, such as ‘quantification and subjective estimation’ and ‘verification of the stabilization of relative frequencies’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24502). However, the progression towards fully structured probabilistic communication is uneven, given that the systematic use of graphical and tabular representations is not made

explicit until the end of CSE, where it becomes highly relevant in Year 4 This is because it is incorporated as a resource for ‘calculation using Laplace's rule and counting techniques in simple and compound experiments (using tree diagrams, tables, etc.)’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744).

In terms of application contexts, the scientific context maintains an explicit and central presence throughout schooling, acting as the backbone of the curricular treatment of probability. Personal and social contexts are incorporated from primary education onwards, although mostly implicitly and with moderate relevance, in line with regulations that establish the need to use ‘varied contexts and include, at least, personal, school, social, scientific and humanistic contexts’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24489). The work context, on the other hand, has a more marginal presence until the final years, which indicates a late incorporation of applications linked to professional fields, coinciding with the moment when the stage acquires a ‘guiding character [...] for incorporation into working life’ (BOE, 2022b, p. 41574).

Finally, analysis of the critical questions shows a clear, albeit delayed, progression in the reflective dimension of probabilistic reasoning. While aspects such as source and process appear implicitly from primary education and become progressively more explicit throughout compulsory secondary education, consideration of context is only consolidated in the 4th year of CSE as an explicit and highly relevant element, linked to the ‘planning and analysis of composite experiments’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744). For its part, reflective interpretation is treated more systematically in secondary education, focusing on the dimension of source and reliability, which the curriculum relates to ‘informed decision-making’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744). This pattern shows that the critical dimension of probabilistic literacy, although present in the regulations through ‘quantification and subjective estimation’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24502) from early stages, is mainly formalized in the final years of compulsory education.

4.2. Results in relation to Dispositional Elements

Table 4 shows that the dispositional elements of probabilistic literacy are generally highly relevant from the early stages of compulsory education, although with varying degrees of explicitness throughout schooling. The dispositions associated with critical thinking, which include the abilities to question, interpret and reflect, appear implicitly and with high relevance from primary education to the first years of secondary education, and are only explicitly formulated in the fourth year of secondary education, indicating a late institutionalization of this dimension. In this final year, the curriculum links this stance to “informed decision-making” and the identification of possible biases or limitations, especially in the “planning and analysis of composite experiments” (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744).

Variables linked to emotions, beliefs, and attitudes follow different trajectories. Beliefs continue to be treated explicitly and with high relevance in all sections, associated with ‘probability as a subjective measure of uncertainty’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498). Emotions, meanwhile, while retaining high relevance, alternate between implicit and explicit

formulations, linked in the regulations to ‘emotional management’ and ‘tolerance to frustration in learning mathematics’ (BOE, 2022a, pp. 24493, 24498). Attitudes remain implicit and of moderate relevance until the first years of secondary education and only become explicit and central in the fourth year of secondary education, where they are consolidated as the basis for critical probabilistic judgement when ‘assessing the scope and impact of these [solutions] from different perspectives’ (BOE, 2022b, p. 41740).

Table 4. *Dispositional elements of Gal (2005) in curriculum regulations*

Category	Variable	3rd and 4th grade	5th and 6th grade	1st, 2nd, and 3rd year of secondary education	4th year of secondary education
Critical Stance	Questioning	(I, H)	(I, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)
	Interpret	(I, H)	(I, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)
	Reflect	(I, H)	(I, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)
Dispositional	Emotions	(E, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Beliefs	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Attitudes	(I, M)	(I, M)	(I, M)	(E, H)
Personal feeling	Uncertainty	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
	Predictability	(E, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)

Note: (x, y), where x is presence and y is relevance; A: Absent, I: Implicit, E: Explicit, H: High, M: Moderate, and L: Low

In the realm of personal feelings, uncertainty is explicitly and highly relevant throughout schooling through the ‘recognition of uncertainty in everyday situations’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498; BOE, 2022b, p. 41777). On the other hand, predictability, despite always maintaining high relevance, varies in its explicitness depending on the stage: in primary school, it is worked on through the ‘identification of certain, possible and impossible events’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498), while in secondary school, it is reiterated with the ‘identification of deterministic and random phenomena’ (BOE, 2022b, p. 41735). Taken together, these results show that, although dispositional dimensions are integrated into the curriculum at an early stage, their explicit formalization and link to critical thinking is concentrated in the final stage of compulsory education.

4.3. Results in relation to the Meanings of Probability

The information collected in Table 5 allows us to analyze the curricular evolution of the different meanings of probability throughout compulsory education, highlighting differences in their degree of explicitness, relevance and continuity according to the educational stage.

Intuitive meaning takes on a prominent role in the second cycle of primary education, where it is explicitly formulated and given high relevance through the ‘identification of certain, possible and impossible events’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498). However, it disappears in the last cycle of this stage, only to reappear later in the first years of secondary education with a renewed explicit and relevant treatment through the ‘identification of deterministic and random phenomena’ (BOE, 2022b, p. 41735). In the fourth year of CSE, this meaning remains implicit and moderately relevant. This non-linear evolution

suggests that intuitive meaning serves as an introduction and conceptual support at key moments in the curriculum, although it loses prominence as more formalized approaches are adopted.

Table 5. *Presence and relevance of probability meanings in curriculum regulations (Presence, Relevance)*

Variable	3rd and 4th grade	5th and 6th grade	1st, 2nd, and 3rd year of secondary education	4th year of secondary education
Intuitive	(E, H)	(A, L)	(E, H)	(I, M)
Classical	(A, L)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
Frequentist	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)	(E, H)
Subjective	(E, H)	(E, H)	(I, H)	(E, H)
Axiomatic	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, L)	(A, L)

Note: A: Absent, I: Implicit, E: Explicit, H: High, M: Moderate and L: Low

The classical meaning shows a more stable progression. It is absent in the early years of primary education and is introduced explicitly and with high relevance in the final cycle of this stage through the ‘calculation of probabilities applying Laplace's rule’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24502), maintaining the same status throughout secondary education. In the final year of compulsory education, this approach is consolidated by requiring the calculation of probabilities ‘applying Laplace's rule and counting techniques’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744). This behaviour reflects a progressive institutionalization of the classical approach, associated with equiprobability and the use of calculation procedures, which is consolidated from the last years of primary school and reinforced in secondary school.

For its part, the frequency meaning is characterized by an explicit and highly relevant presence in all the stages analyzed. It is specified in the regulations through the ‘verification of the stabilization of relative frequencies in repetitive random experiments’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24502). This continuity highlights a sustained curricular commitment to an empirical conception of probability, based on the repetition of experiments and the stabilization of relative frequencies, which is one of the central pillars of the school treatment of probability throughout compulsory education.

Subjective meaning also appears explicitly and with high relevance in primary education, where probability is linked to personal assessment of uncertainty through ‘probability as a subjective measure of uncertainty’ (BOE, 2022a, p. 24498). In the first years of secondary education, its presence becomes implicit, although it remains highly relevant, before returning to an explicit and central role in the fourth year of secondary education, where this degree of belief is integrated into ‘informed decision-making’ (BOE, 2022b, pp. 41739, 41744). Finally, the axiomatic meaning remains absent at all stages of compulsory education, confirming that the curriculum does not contemplate a formal approach based on Kolmogorov's axioms at this educational level.

In summary, the analysis shows that the curriculum combines different meanings of probability, with a clear predominance of the frequentist and classical approaches, a

strategic presence of the intuitive and subjective meaning, and the systematic exclusion of the axiomatic meaning. This distribution highlights a progression that prioritises functional and empirical approaches, gradually incorporating elements of formalization without reaching an axiomatization of the concept of probability in compulsory education.

4.4. Summary

An integrated analysis of the elements of knowledge, dispositional elements and meanings of probability reveals that the compulsory education curriculum in Spain shapes probabilistic literacy geared towards interpreting uncertainty and decision-making in diverse contexts. From the earliest stages, central importance is given to ideas and procedures related to estimation, predictability and frequency meaning, which remain explicit and highly relevant throughout schooling. In contrast, other more structural components, such as independence, certain registers of representation or some critical questions, are incorporated later, with their explicitness concentrated in the final years.

At the dispositional level, personal attitudes, beliefs, emotions, and feelings associated with uncertainty are highly relevant from primary education onwards, although their explicit formulation as curricular objectives intensifies mainly in the final stage of compulsory education. Complementarily, the analysis of the meanings of probability reveals a sustained predominance of the frequentist and classical approaches, together with a selective presence of intuitive and subjective meanings, and the systematic absence of axiomatic meaning.

Overall, the findings suggest that Spanish curriculum regulations consistently integrate cognitive, dispositional, and semantic dimensions in the treatment of probability. However, their articulation across schooling lacks full coherence. While some components are introduced early and progressively consolidated, others are only explicitly formalized in the final years of compulsory education, generating discontinuities that may hinder the systematic development of probabilistic literacy.

5. Discussions and conclusions

The Spanish compulsory education curriculum structures probability teaching in such a way that, in general terms, it progresses from intuitive and subjective approaches in primary education to increasingly formalized forms in compulsory secondary education, especially with regard to the calculation and modeling of random phenomena (Alsina & Vázquez, 2016a; Vázquez & Alsina, 2019a). This approach favors functional probability literacy, aimed at understanding and managing uncertainty in real contexts, in line with approaches that emphasize the need to integrate cognitive and dispositional components into probability education (Cotrado et al., 2022; Fernandes & Diniz, 2022; Jones et al., 2007; Serrano-Díaz, 2022).

Among the main results, the early incorporation of uncertainty, predictability, and variability stands out, contributing to the gradual development of probabilistic and

statistical literacy from the early stages of compulsory education. However, these results contrast with research that advocates for an even earlier introduction of these notions, starting in early childhood education, with the aim of promoting earlier and more continuous contact with probabilistic concepts (Alsina & Salgado, 2019; Alsina & Vásquez, 2025; Batanero et al., 2025; Vásquez & Cabrera, 2022).

In secondary education, consolidating the frequentist and classical meanings provides a solid foundation for calculating probabilities and modeling random situations, reinforcing the procedural and applied nature of the curriculum (Batanero, Begué et al., 2021; Batanero & Álvarez-Arroyo, 2024). Likewise, the explicit incorporation of critical provisions in the 4th year of CSE reinforces the civic dimension of probability by linking it to informed decision-making in contexts of uncertainty, in line with international frameworks that recognize probabilistic literacy as a key competence for responsible participation in the knowledge society (Vásquez et al., 2020; Vásquez, 2020; Vásquez & Rojas, 2020).

Alongside these advances, the analysis also highlights significant limitations. Although some properties studied in secondary education are implicitly based on principles of the axiomatic approach, this meaning is not explicitly addressed, which can hinder the formal understanding of probability in later stages (Batanero, 2005). Added to this is the discontinuity in the treatment of intuitive meaning in the third cycle of primary education, which interrupts the conceptual progression begun in previous years. This break is particularly significant when one considers that probabilistic reasoning evolves through progressive levels, from intuitive and subjective approaches to numerical and formalized interpretations (Batanero et al., 2023). The lack of continuity in these meanings can therefore compromise the gradual transition to more structured forms of such reasoning in higher stages.

Furthermore, the late introduction of key concepts such as independence, together with the delay in the systematic use of graphical representations and in the explicit expression of critical thinking, limits the development of probabilistic reasoning (Batanero et al., 2023). In addition, the connection between the emotional and conceptual aspects of probability is not always made explicit, which can hinder a critical and reflective understanding of uncertainty.

In this context, it is important to consider that the limitations identified in the progression and explanation of certain elements of the curriculum cannot be analyzed in isolation. Previous studies warn that the mere presence of probability in curricula does not guarantee either its understanding by students or effective teaching in the classroom (Batanero et al., 2016). These difficulties are accentuated by the challenges faced by teachers in integrating the different epistemological meanings of probability and their corresponding teaching approaches (Batanero, 2022; Vásquez & Alsina, 2019b). Consequently, there is a need to focus on the development of specific and continuous teacher training that enables teachers to critically interpret the curriculum and develop teaching proposals that allow students to acquire comprehensive probabilistic literacy. Future work should delve deeper into this direction in order to move toward a more

coherent and robust probability curriculum capable of preparing students to deal with uncertainty, risk, and misinformation in contemporary society.

Acknowledgements

Research conducted as part of research projects PID2022-139748NB-100, funded by the State Research Agency MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ and by ERDF, EU, with support from the HUM-886 Research Group (Regional Government of Andalusia, Spain).

Bibliografía

ACARA (2020). *The Australian Curriculum: Mathematics*. <https://www.australiancurriculum.edu.au/f-10-curriculum/mathematics/>

Alsina, Á., & Salgado, M. (2019). Ampliando los conocimientos matemáticos en Educación Infantil: la incorporación de la probabilidad [Expanding mathematical knowledge in Early Childhood Education: the incorporation of probability]. *Revista de Estudios y Experiencias en Educación*, 18(36), 225-240. <https://doi.org/10.21703/rexe.20191836alsina6>

Alsina, Á., & Vásquez, C. (2025). La probabilidad en educación infantil: finalidades, aplicaciones y prácticas de enseñanza [Probability in early childhood education: purposes, applications and teaching practices]. *Revista científica Ecociencia*, 11(4), 45-70. <https://doi.org/10.21855/ecociencia.114.961>

Alsina, Á., & Vásquez, C. (2016a). La enseñanza de la probabilidad en Educación Primaria: el currículo versus el libro de texto. In P.A. Sánchez-Martínez (Eds.), *17 Jornadas para el Aprendizaje y la Enseñanza de las Matemáticas. Actas JAEM 2015* (pp. 1-14). Federación Española de Sociedades de Profesores de Matemáticas.

Alsina, Á., Vásquez, C., Muñoz-Rodríguez, L., & Rodríguez-Muñoz, L. J. (2020). ¿Cómo promover la alfabetización estadística y probabilística en contexto? Estrategias y recursos a partir de la COVID-19 para Educación Primaria [How to promote statistical and probabilistic literacy in context? Strategies and resources from COVID-19 for Primary Education]. *Épsilon*, 104, 99-128.

Alsina, Á., & Vásquez, C. (2016b). La probabilidad en Educación Primaria: de lo que debería enseñarse a lo que se enseña [Probability in Primary Education: From What Should Be Taught to What Is Taught]. *UNO*, 71, 46-52.

Badmus, O. T., Adeniji, S., Getenet, S., & Jita, L. C. (2025). A comparative analysis of Foundation and early primary years mathematics curricula: insights from Australia and South Africa. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2025.2544583>

Batanero, C. (2005). Significados de la probabilidad en la educación secundaria. *Relime*, 8(3), 247-263.

Batanero, C. (2015). Understanding randomness: Challenges for research and teaching. In K. Krainer and N. Vondrová (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Ninth Congress of European Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 34-49). Charles University and ERME.

- Batanero, C. (2022). Training teachers to teach probability: A promising research area. *Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 22(3), 729-734. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42330-022-00234-1>
- Batanero, C., & Álvarez-Arroyo, R. (2024). Teaching and learning of probability. *ZDM Mathematics Education* 56, 5-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-023-01511-5>
- Batanero, C., & Díaz, C. (2007). Probabilidad, grado de creencia y proceso de aprendizaje. In *XIII Jornadas Nacionales de Enseñanza y Aprendizaje de las Matemáticas*, Granada, Federación Española de Profesores de Enseñanza de las Matemáticas.
- Batanero, C., Begué, N., Álvarez-Arroyo, R., & Valenzuela-Ruiz, S. M. (2021). Prospective Mathematics Teachers Understanding of Classical and Frequentist Probability. *Mathematics*, 9(19), 2526. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9192526>
- Batanero, C., Burrill, G., & Reading, C. (2011). Overview: Challenges for teaching statistics in school mathematics and preparing mathematics teachers. In C. Batanero, G. Burrill and C. Reading (Eds.), *Teaching statistics in school mathematics. Challenges for teaching and teacher education: A Joint ISMI/IASE Study* (pp. 407-418). Springer
- Batanero, C., Chernoff, E.J., Engel, J., Lee, H.S., & Sánchez, E. (2016). *Research on Teaching and Learning Probability. ICME-13 Topical Surveys*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31625-3_1
- Batanero, C., Díaz, C., & Contreras, J. M. (2011). *Estadística y probabilidad en educación secundaria* [Statistics and Probability in Secondary Education]. Graó.
- Batanero, C., Godino, J., & Roa, R. (2004). Training Teachers to Teach Probability. *Journal of Statistics Education*, 12(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691898.2004.11910715>
- Batanero, C., Gea, M., & Álvarez-Arroyo, R. (2023). Educação do raciocínio probabilístico [Education of probabilistic reasoning]. *Educação Matemática Pesquisa*, 25(2), 127-144. <https://doi.org/10.23925/1983-3156.2023v25i2p127-144>.
- Bisquerra, R. (2019). *Metodología de la investigación educativa*. La Muralla.
- BOE (2014). *Real Decreto 126/2014, de 28 de febrero, por el que se establece el currículo básico de la Educación Primaria*. Boletín Oficial del Estado.
- BOE (2022a). *Real Decreto 157/2022, de 1 de marzo, por el que se establecen la ordenación y las enseñanzas mínimas de la Educación Primaria*. Boletín Oficial del Estado.
- BOE (2022b). *Real Decreto 217/2022, de 29 de marzo, por el que se establece la ordenación y las enseñanzas mínimas de la Educación Secundaria Obligatoria*. Boletín Oficial del Estado.
- Borges, J., McInerney, C., Exton, C., Harkin, B., & McGarr, O. (2025). The subjective nature of curriculum innovation: The case of computer science students in upper secondary education in Ireland. *Computer Science Education*, 35(4), 820-848. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08993408.2024.2421680>
- Borovcnik, M. (2016). Probabilistic thinking and probability literacy in the context of risk. *Educação Matemática Pesquisa*, 18(3), 1491-1516.

- Bórquez, M. (2025). Decisiones en tiempos de incertidumbre: Cómo nuestro cerebro maneja lo desconocido [Decisions in times of uncertainty: How our brain handles the unknown]. *Ciencia Cognitiva: Revista Electrónica de Divulgación*, 19(1), 20-22.
- CCSSI (2020). *Common Core State Standards for Mathematics*. National Governors Association for Best Practices and the Council of Chief State School Officers.
- Cotrado, B., Burgos, M., & Beltrán-Pellicer, P. (2022). Idoneidad didáctica de materiales curriculares oficiales peruanos de educación secundaria en probabilidad [Didactic suitability of official peruvian Secondary Education curriculum materials in probability]. *Bolema: Boletim de Educação Matemática*, 36(73), 888-922. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-4415v36n73a13>
- Develaki, M. (2025). Uncertainty, Risk, and Decision-Making: Concepts, Guidelines, and Educational Implications. *Science & Education* 34(5), 3123-3154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-024-00544-w>
- Dushimimana, J. C., Urwibutso, A., & Uworwabayeho, A. (2024). Assessing the attitudes of pre-service primary mathematics teachers towards statistics and gender influence. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2315840. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2315840>
- Elliott, E. J. R. (2024). *The Measurement of Subjective Probability*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009401319>
- Fernandes, J. A., & Diniz, L. N. (2022). Ensino de Probabilidade e Estatística na Educação Fundamental da Base Nacional Comum Curricular do Brasil [Teaching probability and statistics in elementary and middle school in Brazil's common national curriculum base]. *Góndola, Enseñanza y Aprendizaje de las Ciencias*, 17(2), 392-406. <https://doi.org/10.14483/23464712.17927>
- Franco, J., & Alsina, Á. (2022). El conocimiento del profesorado de Educación Primaria para enseñar estadística y probabilidad: una revisión sistemática [The knowledge of primary school teachers to teach statistics and probability: a systematic review]. *Aula Abierta*, 51(1), 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.17811/rifie.51.1.2022.7-16>
- Gal, I. (2005). Towards 'probability literacy' for all citizens. In G. Jones (Ed.), *Exploring probability in school: Challenges for teaching and learning* (pp. 43- 71). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/b105829>
- García-Alonso, I., Vásquez, C., & Alsina, Á. (2025). Panorama curricular de la alfabetización temprana en estadística y probabilidad [Curriculum overview of early literacy in statistics and probability]. *Profesorado, Revista de Currículum y Formación del Profesorado*, 29(1), 265-294. <https://doi.org/10.30827/profesorado.v29i1.30849>
- Gilovich, T., Griffin, D., & Kahneman, D. (2002). *Heuristics and Biases: The Psychology of Intuitive Judgment*. Cambridge University Press.
- Godino, J., Batanero, C., & Cañizares, M. J. (1996). *Azar y probabilidad*. Síntesis.
- Gómez, E., Contreras, J., & Batanero, C. (2015). Significados de la probabilidad en libros de texto para educación primaria en Andalucía [Meanings of probability in primary school textbooks used in Andalucía]. In C. Fernández, M. Molina and N. Planas (Eds.), *Investigación en Educación Matemática XIX* (pp. 69-72). SEIEM.

- Hokor, E. K. (2023). Probabilistic thinking for life: The decision-making ability of professionals in uncertain situations. *International Journal of Studies in Education and Science*, 4(1), 31-54. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijses.44>
- Jones, G., Langrall, C., & Mooney, E. (2007). Research in probability: Responding to classroom realities. In F. Lester (Ed.), *Second handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (Vol. 2, pp. 909-955). Information Age Publishing and NCTM.
- Kolmogorov, A. N. (1933). *Grundbegriffe der Wahrscheinlichkeitsrechnung*. Springer
- Krippendorff, K. (2019). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*. SAGE. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071878781>
- Laplace, P. S. (1814). *A philosophical essay on Probabilities*. Chapman & Hall
- López, C., & Gómez, P. (2022). Probabilidad en diferentes países del mundo: enseñanza de la probabilidad en educación primaria [Probability in different countries of the world: teaching probability in primary education]. *Educación Matemática*, 34(3), 42-64. <https://doi.org/10.24844/EM3403.02>
- McPhail, G. (2021). The search for deep learning: a curriculum coherence model. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 53(4), 420-434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2020.1748231>
- MINEDUC (2012). *Matemática educación básica: Bases curriculares* [Basic education mathematics: Curricular bases]. Unidad de Curriculum y Evaluación.
- MOE (2015). *The New Zealand curriculum: Mathematics standards for years 1-8*. Ministry of Education of New Zealand.
- Nacarato, A. M., & Grando, R. C. (2014). The role of language in building probabilistic thinking. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 13(2), 93-103. <https://doi.org/10.52041/serj.v13i2.283>
- NCTM. (2003). *Principles and standards for school mathematics*. National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Neuendorf, K. A. (2016). *The Content Analysis Guidebook*. Sage.
- Ortiz, J. J., Mohamed, N., Serrano, L., & Rodríguez, J. D. (2007). Comprensión de la idea de juego equitativo en maestros en formación [Understanding the Idea of Fair Game in Preservice Teachers]. In P. Bolea, M. Camacho, P. Flores, B. Gómez, J. Murillo and M. T. González (Eds.), *Investigación en Educación Matemática. Comunicaciones de los grupos de investigación. XI Simposio* (pp. 235-244). SEIEM.
- Reyes-Astorga, M., Díaz-Levicoy, D., & Rodríguez-Alveal, F. (2025). Evaluación del pensamiento probabilístico en futuros profesores de matemática en Educación Secundaria [Assessment of probabilistic thinking in future mathematics teachers in Secondary Education]. *Revista Espacios*, 46(1), 187-203. <https://doi.org/10.48082/espacios-a25v46n01p15>
- REB (2015). *Competency-Based Curriculum. Summary of curriculum framework pre-primary touppe secondary*. Rwanda Education Board.
- Schoen, R. C., LaVenía, M., Chicken, E., Razzouk, R., & Kisa, Z. (2019). Increasing secondary-level teachers' knowledge in statistics and probability: Results from a

- randomized controlled trial of a professional development program. *Cogent Education*, 6(1), 1613799. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2019.1613799>
- Schmidt, W. H., & Houang, R. T. (2012). Curricular coherence and the Common Core State Standards for Mathematics. *Educational Researcher*, 41(8), 294-308. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X12464517>
- Schulz, L., Rollwage, M., Dolan, R. J., & Fleming, S. M. (2020). Dogmatism manifests in lowered information search under uncertainty. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 117(49), 31527-31534. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2009641117>
- Serrano - Díaz, G. (2022). La definición de probabilidad y su enseñanza a partir de sus significados: reflexiones [The definition of probability and its teaching from its meanings: reflections]. *Investigación y Postgrado*, 37(2), 25-38. <https://doi.org/10.56219/investigacionpostgrado.v37i2.1456>
- Vásquez, C. (2020). Educación Estocástica en el aula escolar: una herramienta para formar ciudadanos de sostenibilidad [Stochastic Education in the classroom: A tool for educating citizens for sustainability]. *Matemáticas, Educación y Sociedad*, 3(2), 1-20.
- Vásquez, C., & Alsina, Á. (2017). Lenguaje probabilístico: un camino para el desarrollo de la alfabetización probabilística. Un estudio de caso en el aula de Educación Primaria [Probabilistic language: A path for the development of probabilistic literacy. A case study in a Primary Education classroom]. *Bolema. Boletim de Educação Matemática*. 31(57), 454-478. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-4415v31n57a22>
- Vásquez, C., & Alsina, Á. (2019a). Observing mathematics teaching practices to promote professional development: An analysis of approaches to probability. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(3), 719-733. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5866>
- Vásquez, C., & Alsina, Á. (2019b). Conocimiento especializado del profesorado de educación básica para la enseñanza de la probabilidad [Primary Education teachers' specialized knowledge to teach probability]. *Profesorado, Revista de Currículum y Formación del Profesorado*, 23(1), 393-419. <https://doi.org/10.30827/profesorado.v23i1.9160>
- Vásquez, C., & Cabrera, G. (2022). La estadística y la probabilidad en los currículos de matemáticas de educación infantil y primaria de seis países representativos en el campo [Statistics and probability in early childhood and primary mathematics curricula in six countries representative of the field]. *Educación Matemática*, 34(2), 245-274. <https://doi.org/10.24844/em3402.09>
- Vásquez, C., & Rojas F. (2020). Enseñar probabilidad para formar ciudadanos en sostenibilidad: ¿Qué sabemos de la COVID-19 y su propagación? [Teaching Probability to Educate Citizens for Sustainability: What do we know about COVID-19 and its spread?]. *Uno*, 89, 22-29.
- Vásquez, C., Rodríguez-Muñiz, L. J., Muñiz-Rodríguez, L., & Alsina, Á. (2020). ¿Cómo promover la alfabetización probabilística en contexto? Estrategias y recursos a partir de la COVID-19 para la Educación Secundaria [How to promote probability literacy in context? Strategies and resources from COVID-19 for Secondary Education]. *Números*, 104, 239-260.

Young, M. (2013). Overcoming the crisis in curriculum theory: a knowledge-based approach. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 45(2), 101-118.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2013.764505>